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Exploring the production-perception link in voice quality: vowel formants as correlates of VPA longitudinal settings

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the acoustic-perceptual link for longitudinal supralaryngeal voice quality settings outlined by the Vocal Profile Analysis (VPA) protocol (Laver et al, 1991; Beck, 2007). As a quasi-permanent attribute shaped by both physiological and socially learned factors, voice quality is fundamental to fields like Sociophonetics and Forensic Phonetics. While often evaluated perceptually through protocols like the VPA, the systematic link between these auditory judgments and measurable acoustic parameters requires further validation. To this end, this study tests the hypothesis that vowel formants serve as acoustic correlates for longitudinal settings, focusing on larynx height and lip protrusion/spreading as perceptually assessed through scalar degrees in the VPA. The analysis was based on 100 geographically stratified speech samples from the Brazilian Portuguese Forensic Corpus (CFPB), for which detailed VPA profiles were available. The first four formants of vowels /a/, /ɛ/, and /ɔ/ were extracted and analyzed using Spearman's correlation and Welch's ANOVA. Results revealed robust, moderate-to-strong positive correlations between larynx height degrees and all formants, confirming a global spectral shift. For lip configuration, correlations were more specific and modest in magnitude; they were strongest for the second formant (F2) but were also reflected in more global spectral measures, being evident primarily in non-back vowels. These findings demonstrate a systematic yet setting-specific production-perception relationship: larynx height is cued by a broad spectral pattern, while lip configuration relies on a more localized, yet perceptually integrated, acoustic cue. This work strengthens the empirical foundation of the VPA and refines our understanding of the acoustic basis of voice quality perception.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Voice quality, metaphorically described as a quasi-permanent auditory colouring of an individual speaker's voice, arises from the combination of laryngeal, supralaryngeal, and muscular tension activities (Laver, 2009). Shaped by both physiological and socially learned factors, it carries significant indexical value, making it a fundamental object of study in fields such as Sociophonetics and Forensic Phonetics. While often approached through perceptual analysis, a critical step toward the objective characterization of voice quality lies in establishing systematic links between auditory perception and measurable acoustic parameters (Kreiman; Vanlancker-Sidtis; Gerratt, 2003).

The Vocal Profile Analysis (VPA) protocol (Laver et al., 1991; Beck, 2007) provides a structured framework for such perceptual analysis, decomposing voice quality into a set of *articulatory settings*, defined as long-term muscular configurations that tend to affect all speech segments. Because of their global and persistent influence, these settings underpin the strong indexical potential of voice quality, conveying information about a speaker's physical, psychological, and social characteristics (Laver, 2000).

Developed through collaboration between phoneticians and speech-language therapists, the protocol has evolved through several versions. Its current formulation (Beck, 2007) comprises 56 settings, organized into vocal-tract (supralaryngeal) features, overall muscular tension, and phonation (laryngeal) features, as well as supplementary sections addressing prosodic features and temporal organization.

Trained judges evaluate each setting on a 6-degree scale according to its perceived deviation from a neutral reference, a baseline with specified acoustic and physiological correlates. This neutral reference serves strictly as a comparative benchmark and should not be conflated with notions of normality; indeed, most speakers deviate from it in at least one setting. The resulting pattern of non-neutral settings thus constitutes a speaker's vocal profile, functioning as a perceptual representation of their voice quality.

Although articulatory settings exert a global influence on speech production, individual segments vary in their susceptibility to the effects of a given setting due to their intrinsic phonetic properties. For this reason, both perceptual evaluation and acoustic characterization within the VPA framework rely on the notion of key segments, defined as phonetic units in which the effects of a given setting are most perceptually and acoustically salient (Beck, 2007).

Supralaryngeal settings, which refer to long-term configurations of the vocal tract from the lips to the laryngeal region, are expected to induce systematic shifts in its resonant frequencies, or formants. Therefore, vocalic segments, which are highly sensitive to changes in

vocal-tract configuration, generally function as key segments for revealing the acoustic consequences of supralaryngeal settings.

Despite this well-established articulation-acoustic link, the empirical mapping between perceptual degrees in the VPA and their acoustic correlates remains underexplored. Moreover, although VPA evaluation is systematic and conducted by trained judges, it relies on listeners' inferences about articulatory configurations from the acoustic signal and therefore involves an irreducible degree of perceptual subjectivity. Investigating such acoustic-perceptual relationships thus serves not only to identify acoustic correlates of perceptual judgments, but also to assess the internal coherence and practical validity of the VPA as a voice quality assessment instrument, insofar as specific acoustic patterns are expected *a priori* from established articulatory-acoustic correlations.

Against this background, the present study, part of a broader project on the acoustic correlates of voice quality and their forensic applications (Passetti, 2023; 2025), addresses this gap by examining the relationship between vowel formant frequencies and the VPA-based perceptual evaluation of longitudinal settings, a subclass of supralaryngeal settings that modify the effective length of the vocal tract.

We focus on two types of longitudinal settings: larynx height and lip configuration. Each dimension can be grouped along a continuum between a pair of opposing settings, being rated on a 13-degree scale (Beck, 2007), in which the central value represents a neutral reference. The larynx-height continuum spans from lowered to raised larynx, whereas the lip-configuration continuum spans from lip rounding/protrusion to lip spreading.

From an articulatory-acoustic perspective, longitudinal settings, by modifying the shape and effective length of the vocal tract, are expected to induce systematic shifts in its resonant frequencies, or formants. Consequently, articulatory configurations associated with vocal-tract shortening, such as raised larynx and lip spreading settings, are expected to manifest acoustically as increases in formant values.

Therefore, in this study, the acoustic dimension is operationalized through vowel formant frequencies, key segments which tend to reflect the spectral consequences of the supralaryngeal settings, while the perceptual dimension is represented by the VPA degrees assigned to each longitudinal setting. The relationship between these two variables is the focus of the analysis.

On the basis of this articulation–acoustic–perceptual relationship, we advance the general hypothesis that higher VPA degrees along longitudinal setting continua will be

positively correlated with vowel formant values, reflecting progressive vocal-tract shortening. This general hypothesis is tested through the following specific predictions:

(H1a) Increases in VPA ratings along the larynx-height continuum (from lowered toward raised larynx) will correlate positively with all vowel formant values.

(H1b) Increases in VPA ratings along the lip-configuration continuum (from rounding/protrusion toward spreading) will likewise correlate positively with vowel formant values.

To test these, we analyzed 100 geographically stratified speech samples from the *Corpus Forense do Português Brasileiro* (CFPB – Brazilian Portuguese Forensic Corpus), for which detailed VPA profiles were previously established (Passetti, 2023). The first four formants (F1–F4) of the vowels /a/, /ɛ/, and /ɔ/ were extracted and subjected to inferential statistical analysis, including Spearman’s rank correlation and Welch’s ANOVA, to investigate their association with the perceptual scales.

By empirically testing this acoustic-perceptual link, this research aims to strengthen the empirical foundations of the VPA protocol and enhance its applicability in contexts that demand objective voice description, such as Forensic Phonetics.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 DATA SOURCE

This study utilized the dataset curated by Passetti (2023; 2025), which consists of 100 semi-spontaneous speech samples from the *Corpus Forense do Português Brasileiro* (CFPB – Brazilian Portuguese Forensic Corpus) (BRASIL, Portaria nº 934-Ditec/PF, 2020) and their corresponding vocal profiles, generated from the Vocal Profile Analysis (VPA) assessment in the author’s 2023 study. The speech samples consist of male Federal and Civil Police officers aged 25–50 and are geographically stratified across Brazil’s macroregions (Center-West: n=8; Northeast: n=27; North: n=9; Southeast: n=42; South: n=14)⁴. Each sample contains 40 seconds of continuous, high-quality audio (WAVE format, ≥ 22.05 kHz, 16-bit) along with a corresponding TextGrid file that includes three annotation tiers. The vowel segments /a/, /ɛ/ and /ɔ/ used in the present analysis are labeled in one of the tiers.

2.2. PERCEPTUAL DATA PROCESSING

⁴ Data were proportionally stratified according to the 2021 Continuous National Household Sample Survey conducted by IBGE.

This study focused on the longitudinal supralaryngeal settings from the VPA profiles. The initial proposal was to analyze only those settings rated as non-neutral in at least 10% of the speakers. However, since most of these settings form diametrically opposed pairs along a 13-degree continuum (Beck; Schaeffler, 2015), we opted to aggregate them, treating the neutral setting as the central point (degree 0). In the resulting aggregated scales, positive values correspond to the original VPA degrees, while negative values result from the inversion of the opposing setting. This strategy expanded the levels of the variable and optimized the analyses, enabling more robust correlations and the inclusion of settings that, if analyzed individually, would have occurred below the 10% sample threshold.

Based on this approach, the scalar degrees for larynx height (from lowered to raised) and lip configuration (from rounding/protrusion to spreading) were selected and reorganized into continuous numerical scales for statistical correlation with the acoustic data. The labiodentalization setting, although part of the same longitudinal category, was excluded from the analysis due to insufficient data in the corpus.

The distribution of the aggregated degrees among speakers for the selected setting pairs is presented in Table 1. Although the theoretical scale ranges from -6 to 6, the observed occurrences are concentrated between -2 and 3.

Table 1. Distribution of longitudinal supralaryngeal setting pairs among speakers.

Vocal tract feature	Setting pairs	Naming convention	Aggregated scale degrees					
			-2	-1	0	1	2	3
Larynx height	Lowered larynx + raised larynx	LX_LxR	5	17	54	19	4	1
Lip configuration	Lip rounding/protrusion + lip spreading	LI_RxS	1	5	89	4	1	0

Thus, the two perceptual variables used in the statistical analysis are defined as follows:

- a) Larynx Height (LX_LxR): An ordinal, bipolar numerical scale where a value of 0 represents the neutral setting, negative values represent a perceptually lowered larynx, and positive values represent a raised larynx.
- b) Lip Configuration (LI_RxS): An ordinal, bipolar numerical scale where a value of 0 represents the neutral setting, negative values represent lip rounding/protrusion, and positive values represent lip spreading.

The distribution of setting degrees reveals a concentration of speakers around the central grades (-1, 0, 1), with a decreasing frequency towards the extremes, which in many cases are represented by only one speaker. This scarcity at the distribution tails imposes limitations on the statistical analyses, as the acoustic parameters corresponding to few individuals may not adequately represent the behavior of the group.

2.3 ACOUSTIC DATA EXTRACTION AND PROCESSING

Acoustic parameters were extracted from the 100 speech samples using PRAAT (Boersma; Weenink, 2022). For each speaker, appropriate configuration parameters (such as "formant ceiling" and "number of formants") were established using the *formants.praat* script (Arantes, 2023), which validates formant tracking by superimposing the spectral peaks of FFT and LPC. This configuration was applied to all occurrences of the vowels /a/, /ɛ/, and /ɔ/ for the respective speaker. Contextual data for each vowel occurrence, including word transcription, phonetic context, and stress, were also recorded. A custom script developed for this research, *script_vowel_formants* (Carvalho, 2025), was then used to extract the first four formants at each vowel midpoint.

The formant values were then converted from the physical Hertz scale to the psychoacoustic Equivalent Rectangular Bandwidth (ERB) scale. This choice follows the premise that psychoacoustic scales such as ERB more adequately reflect the nonlinearity of human auditory sensitivity to sound (Glasberg & Moore, 1990). Consequently, equal increments on the ERB scale tend to correspond to equivalent perceptual differences. This conversion allowed formant variations to be analyzed in terms of their perceptual relevance and yielded more consistent correlations with VPA judgments. The formula proposed by Traunmüller (1997) was used for this transformation:

$$ERB(f) = 11.17 \cdot \ln\left(\frac{f + 312}{f + 14675}\right) + 43$$

Following tabulation, the data underwent cleaning and supplementation through these steps:

- 1) Removal of missegmented vowels (e.g., mid-close, post-tonic, or non-target vowels);
- 2) Per-speaker outlier filtering: exclusion of tokens where F1 or F2 fell beyond ± 2 standard deviations from the speaker's mean, to eliminate measurement or segmentation errors and retain typical productions;

- 3) Manual verification of persistent outliers: outliers were initially identified by calculating thresholds across all speakers and were excluded only upon confirmation of a measurement error;
- 4) Supplementation of underrepresented vowels: at least one token of /ɔ/ (absent in five speakers) and /ɛ/ (absent in one speaker) was added to ensure minimal representation per vowel;
- 5) Speaker-level averaging of formants: for each vowel, mean F1 to F4 values were calculated from all of its occurrences per speaker. This was done by first averaging within stressed and pre-stressed contexts separately, then computing the mean of those two averages to balance unequal token counts;
- 6) Data integration: the mean formant values per vowel were linked to each speaker's VPA scale ratings, creating a unified dataset for acoustic-perceptual correlation analysis.

The final dataset comprised 3170 vowel tokens, distributed as follows: 64% /a/, 25% /ɛ/, and 11% /ɔ/. This discrepancy was expected, as near-open vowels occur predominantly in stressed positions, with exceptions arising from dialectal variations. Furthermore, an uneven distribution of vowels across speakers was observed, both in quantity and stress: only 63% of speakers had at least three occurrences of each vowel, while 21% had only one production of /ɔ/; for 12% of speakers, the near-open vowels occurred exclusively in pre-tonic position. It is important to note that these asymmetries in the corpus composition may have compromised the robustness of the correlations, as reduced samples can amplify contextual factors, and differences in stress directly affect acoustic parameters.

For the statistical analysis, acoustic variables were derived from speaker-level formant values, described in step (5) of data processing. Each of these speaker-vowel-formant means (in ERB) was converted to a z-score relative to the distribution of that same measure across all speakers in the corpus, producing the foundational measure for the study, the *vowel-formant deviation*, which expresses each speaker's production as a comparable, perception-relevant deviation from the corpus norm.

Using the *vowel-formant deviation* as a building block, derived variables were produced by aggregating these standardized deviations in two main ways: (1) across vowels for a given formant, and (2) across formants for a given vowel. A third, global index was then derived by averaging the results of the second aggregation across all three vowels. This yielded three derived indices, each designed to isolate the contribution of a specific acoustic dimension to the perceptual rating:

- a) The *formant-generalized deviation* (fx_G) isolates the role of a specific formant regardless of the vowel, by averaging its value across vowel contexts. Comparing the strength of correlation across the four fx_G indices reveals which formant, if any, is the most salient perceptual cue for longitudinal settings.
- b) The *vowel-spectral deviation* (f_V) isolates the role of a specific vowel by integrating the shift of all four formants within it. Comparing the correlations of the three f_V indices (for /a/, /ε/, and /ɔ/) identifies whether certain vowels act as more informative key segments for the perception of longitudinal settings.
- c) The *global spectral deviation* (f_G) tests the integrated hypothesis: whether a speaker's overall supralaryngeal spectral configuration (formants F1 to F4 averaged across all three vowels) is the primary acoustic correlate underlying the perceptual judgment, as predicted.

This approach identifies which parameters best predict listeners' evaluations. A significant finding would demonstrate that the well-established articulation-acoustic relationship (e.g., between vocal tract length and formant values) is consistently reflected in the auditory judgments made using the VPA protocol, thereby providing empirical support for its pertinence and efficacy as a perceptual-auditory tool for voice quality analysis.

The following table summarizes these variables:

Table 2. Acoustic Variables for Statistical Analysis

Category	Description	Naming Convention
<i>Vowel-formant deviation</i>	Mean value of formant fx across all occurrences of vowel V for speaker S , standardized as a z-score against the corpus distribution. Indicates how a speaker's typical production of a specific formant for a specific vowel deviates from the corpus norm.	fx_V (e.g., fI_A)
<i>Formant-generalized deviation</i>	Mean of a speaker's <i>vowel-formant deviation</i> (fx_V) for a specific formant fx across the three vowels (/a/, /ε/, /ɔ/). Represents the speaker's vowel-averaged deviation from the corpus norm for that particular formant.	fx_G (e.g., fI_G)
<i>Vowel-spectral deviation</i>	Mean of a speaker's <i>vowel-formant deviation</i> for all four formants (F1–F4) of a specific vowel V . Represents the overall spectral configuration of that vowel for a speaker, relative to corpus norms.	f_V (e.g., f_EH)
<i>Global spectral deviation</i>	Mean of a speaker's three <i>vowel-spectral deviation</i> indices (f_V). Represents a speaker's	f_G

	overall, vowel-averaged spectral shift across the vocal tract, providing a single global measure of supralaryngeal configuration.	
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2.4 STATISTICAL METHODS

The investigation of correlations between acoustic parameters and the degrees of longitudinal supralaryngeal settings was conducted using Spearman's rank correlation and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), performed with the JAMOVI statistical software (The Jamovi Project, 2025).

Spearman's correlation was chosen to assess monotonic relationships as it is appropriate for relating continuous variables (formants) to ordinal ones (VPA degrees), without assuming normality or linearity. Analyses were run under two conditions: 1) full sample (N=100) to capture general trends, and 2) excluding the neutral degree to focus on non-neutral settings, despite the reduced sample size and created discontinuity. Results report the coefficient (ρ), p-value ($\alpha = 0.05$), and effect size ($\rho < 0.3$: weak; $0.3 \leq \rho < 0.5$: moderate; $0.5 \leq \rho < 0.8$: strong; $\rho \geq 0.8$: very strong).

Welch's ANOVA was used to verify formant mean differences across setting degrees, as it does not assume equal group variances. The Games-Howell post-hoc test was applied for pairwise comparisons. This analysis tested for systematic correspondence, not causality. Results report the F-value, degrees of freedom (df1, df2), p-value ($\alpha = 0.05$), and sample size (N), excluding degrees with N=1. Subsequently, to evaluate the perceptual significance of significant differences found, the z-scores were converted back to ERB units, thereby expressing the effect size in perceptually relevant terms. A 0.4 ERB threshold, a conservative perceptual benchmark from phonetic literature, was adopted for evaluating effect relevance.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 3 presents the statistical results for larynx height settings (lowered vs. raised; LX_LxR), focusing on the aggregated acoustic measures.

Table 3. Statistical tests for larynx height settings (LX_LxR)

Variable	Spearman Correlation		Welch's ANOVA
	Condition 1 (N=100)	Condition 2 (N=46)	N = 99; df1 = 4

	ρ	p	ρ	p	F	df2	p
$f1_G$	0.371	*	0.512	*	4.34	13.80	0.018
$f2_G$	0.485	*	0.579	*	7.05	13.00	0.003
$f3_G$	0.501	*	0.614	*	11.19	14.00	*
$f4_G$	0,481	*	0.608	*	16.34	14.00	*
f_A	0.624	*	0.719	*	16.18	14.20	*
f_EH	0.613	*	0.718	*	15.63	13.40	*
f_OH	0.485	*	0.614	*	8.37	14.80	*
f_G	0.659	*	0.756	*	19.75	14.10	*
* p < 0,001							

Spearman correlations for these aggregated measures showed positive monotonic relationships, ranging from moderate to strong in Condition 1 (N=100; $0.371 \leq \rho \leq 0.659$, $p < .001$). These associations strengthened to strong levels in Condition 2 (N=46; $0.512 \leq \rho \leq 0.756$, $p < .001$), with the *global spectral deviation* (f_G) and the *vowel-spectral deviation* indices for /a/ (f_A) and /ɛ/ (f_EH) consistently yielding the highest coefficients. Regarding the *formant-generalized deviations*, F1 showed relatively weaker correlations in comparison with higher formants.

This finding at the aggregate level is underpinned by a consistent pattern observed in the primary measures (*vowel-formant deviations*). Significant correlations of moderate to strong magnitude were also found for nearly all individual formants (F1–F4) across the three vowels in both conditions, with similar coefficient values. This demonstrates that the perceptual judgment is not based on a single acoustic cue, but is instead cued by a global spectral shift that tends to systematically affect all formants and vowels. A notable exception to this pattern was for the second formant frequency for /ɔ/ ($f2_OH$), which showed no significant correlation.

Welch's ANOVA confirmed highly significant overall differences in formant measures across the larynx height degrees for all eight aggregated measures (e.g.: for f_G : $F(4, 14.10) = 19.75$, $p < .001$). Post-hoc Games-Howell tests identified 33 statistically significant pairwise differences. The measures f_A , f_EH , and f_G were the most discriminative, showing

significant differences in 6 to 7 pairwise comparisons. The contrasts between degrees -1|0 and -1|1 (i.e., pairwise contrasts between ordinal degrees of larynx height in the VPA protocol, where -1 = lowered, 0 = neutral, +1 = raised) emerged as the most perceptually critical, accounting for significant differences in 6 and 8 measures, respectively.

The perceptual relevance of these differences was confirmed by their magnitude. Effect sizes ranged from 0.28 to 1.06 ERB, with 23 out of the 33 significant pairwise differences (69.7%) meeting or exceeding the 0.4 ERB perceptual relevance threshold. The -1|1 contrast was particularly salient, surpassing this threshold across all eight measures (0.49–0.77 ERB).

In contrast to the robust and systematic patterns observed for larynx height settings, the acoustic correlates of lip configuration settings (rounding vs. spreading; LI_RxS) presented a more limited and specific profile. The following analysis, based on Table 4, focuses on the acoustic measures that showed relatively stronger associations or approached statistical significance, providing a clearer picture of the emerging trends.

Table 4. Statistical Tests for LI_RxS

Variable	Spearman Correlation				Welch's ANOVA		
	Condition 1 (N=100)		Condition 2 (N=11)		N = 98; df1 = 2		
	ρ	p	ρ	p	F	df2	p
$f2_A$	0.233	0.020	0.709	0.015	0.98	5.06	0.436*
$f2_EH$	0.214	0.033	0.518	0.102*	1.25	5.07	0.363*
$f2_G$	0.218	0.029	0.680	0.021	1.46	6.35	0.301*
f_A	0.163	0.106*	0.797	0.003	0.87	6.18	0.466*
f_EH	0.161	0.110*	0.548	0.081*	0.44	4.98	0.667*
f_G	0.140	0.164*	0.655	0.029	0.46	5.44	0.656*

* Statistically non-significant results ($p > 0.05$).

As shown in Table 4, Welch's ANOVA revealed no statistically significant differences in formant means across the degrees of lip configuration for any of the analyzed measures. In contrast, Spearman correlation analysis revealed an acoustic-perceptual relationship, although more nuanced than for larynx height settings.

This relationship was initially evidenced by the *vowel-spectral deviation* indices (f_A , f_G , f_EH). While these measures showed only non-significant trends in Condition 1, strong

and significant correlations emerged in Condition 2 for f_{A} ($\rho = 0.80$, $p = .003$) and f_{G} ($\rho = 0.66$, $p = .029$), with a similar trend for f_{EH} ($\rho = 0.55$, $p = .081$). The emergence of these clear associations in Condition 2, despite the small sample size ($N = 11$), indicates that the substantial acoustic dispersion of the 89 speakers rated as neutral in Condition 1 likely masked the underlying association. This pattern suggests that a perceptually relevant global spectral signature exists, but its statistical detectability is contingent on isolating speakers who manifest the setting as non-neutral.

A more precise picture emerged from the analysis of individual formants, which identified the second formant (F2) as the primary acoustic correlate. This finding mirrored the aggregated results, with significant correlations observed for the non-back vowels /a/ and /ɛ/ ($f2_{A}$, $f2_{EH}$) and the global F2 measure ($f2_{G}$), but not for the back vowel /ɔ/ ($f2_{OH}$). These F2 correlations were statistically significant in the full sample (Condition 1) and intensified to strong magnitudes in the restricted sample of non-neutral speakers (Condition 2). Although $f2_{EH}$ did not reach statistical significance in Condition 2 ($\rho = 0.52$, $p = .102$), its positive trend reinforces the overall pattern.

This consistent prominence of F2 is acoustically grounded, as labial configuration primarily modulates the length of the front cavity, a key determinant of F2 frequency (Fant, 1973, *apud* Lima et al., 2007). The consistent lack of correlation for the back vowel /ɔ/, however, suggests it is acoustically less sensitive to this setting, likely because its inherent phonological rounding restricts the scope for substantive phonetic variation in lip configuration. No other formant exhibited a comparable pattern of significant correlations or consistent trends across conditions.

The marked difference in the acoustic correlates between larynx height and lip configuration is likely to stem from their distinct physiological mechanisms, an effect compounded by their differential occurrence in the speaker sample. Lowering or raising the larynx directly alters the length of the laryngopharynx, effectively shortening or elongating the entire vocal tract tube. This action induces an overall shift of all its resonant frequencies (Fant, 1960), producing a more potent and broad spectral change that is readily detectable acoustically. This robust effect was clearly captured in the larger sample of non-neutral speakers for this setting ($N=46$).

In contrast, lip protrusion or spreading represents a more localized perturbation, primarily altering the length of the front cavity only, with a consequently more selective acoustic effect predominantly on F2. This subtler acoustic signature, combined with a very

small sample of non-neutral speakers (N=11), explains the more conditional and vowel-dependent correlations observed for LI_RxS.

Furthermore, this discrepancy in acoustic robustness may be further influenced by the greater potential movement range of the larynx compared to the lips, and by the fact that larynx height, unlike lip rounding, does not carry a primary phonological function in Brazilian Portuguese, potentially allowing for greater articulatory freedom in its realization for voice quality purposes.

In summary, these findings provide a nuanced and setting-specific validation of the study's hypotheses. Hypothesis H1a receives strong and consistent support: the positive correlations between VPA ratings of larynx height and global spectral indices (such as f_G) confirm that listeners' judgments robustly track the uniform formant shift expected from vocal tract lengthening/shortening. Hypothesis H1b, on the other hand, finds qualified and layered support, reflecting the more localized articulatory nature of lip configuration. The clearest acoustic correlate is the F2 shift, aligning with the primary acoustic consequence of front-cavity modification. Broader spectral effects (f_A , f_G) also emerge, but their detection depends critically on controlling for the neutral degree and the specific vowel context, underscoring the cue's subtlety and context-dependency.

3 FINAL REMARKS

This study set out to investigate the acoustic-perceptual link for longitudinal supralaryngeal voice quality settings, testing the central hypothesis that perceptual degrees of the Vocal Profile Analysis protocol would correlate systematically with vowel formants. The results provide a clear but nuanced answer, demonstrating that this link is robust yet fundamentally shaped by the underlying articulator.

Hypothesis H1a, related to larynx height settings, was strongly supported by a correlation with global spectral shifts, affecting all formants as captured by indices like f_G . Hypothesis H1b, related to lip configuration, received partial and more complex support. While positive correlations emerged with broader spectral measures, the clearest and most consistent correlate was the shift in the second formant (F2), a relationship modulated by vowel context.

This delineation of distinct acoustic correlates, from broad spectral trends to specific formant-based cues, represents a significant step toward the empirical validation of the VPA protocol. It moves the framework from a primarily descriptive system toward one with quantifiable acoustic foundations.

These findings open several productive paths for future work. A key next step involves investigating the interaction of these settings with other supralaryngeal settings, likely requiring multivariate approaches. Future studies could also profitably explore a wider range of acoustic measures, such as spectral tilt or source-related parameters, and employ complementary statistical models to better capture the non-linear relationships that may characterize voice quality perception. Furthermore, building a more balanced corpus to adequately represent non-neutral degrees, including underrepresented settings like labiodentalization, will be crucial. Ultimately, this research trajectory contributes to the larger goal of refining objective voice analysis methods, promising enhanced applications in fields such as Forensic Phonetics and clinical voice assessment.

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COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data, code, and materials supporting the findings of this study are available on a public repository hosted on OSF <<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/CENJY>>. All content in the repository is shared under the Academic Free License (AFL) 3.0 and does not contain any personal information that could identify the participants.

CFPB source files are not available due to legal and ethical reasons. Access to these materials has been granted only to the research team, upon formal request. Those interested in accessing the materials should submit a formal request to *Serviço de Perícias em Audiovisual e Eletrônicos* department with the Brazilian Federal Police (SEPAEL/DPER/INC/DITEC/PF) <inc.ditec@dpf.gov.br>. Instructions for making a request are available at Resolution N°. 934-DITEC/PF of July 30, 2020, and the timelines associated with processing requests are provided by the department responsible for the repository.

AI USE STATEMENT

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (OpenAI) and DeepSeek for assistance in translation, English language revision, and support in the development of a script for extracting acoustic measurements (script_vowel_formant), with moderate contribution. All content was reviewed and edited by the authors, who take full responsibility for the manuscript.

ETHICS

This work was approved by the Comitê de Ética em Pesquisa em Seres Humanos at UFSCar on July 23, 2023 under approval number 69491123.0.0000.5504. Informed consent was waived, as all data used in this study were derived from secondary sources based on information from human participants, and no new data were collected. These data were collected, coded, and anonymized in accordance with the procedures of the Corpus Forense do Português Brasileiro (BRASIL, Portaria nº 934-Ditec/PF, 2020), compiled by Setor de Perícias em Audiovisual e Eletrônicos, Instituto Nacional de Criminalística, Brazilian Federal Police (SEPAEL/INC/PF).

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